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COMPUTER-BASED TEST ENTRANCE EXAMINATION: EVIDENCE FROM POST-UTME CANDIDATES IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA.

¹Dr (Mrs) Nwogwugwu Chidirim Esther; ²Ovat Sylvia Victor
&

³Dr (Mrs) Idika, Delight. O.

Department of Educational Foundations, Guidance and Counseling,

University of Calabar, Calabar.

¹chidirimesther66@yahoo.com; ²sylviaovat@gmail.com; ³delightuidika@yahoo.com.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate on the computer-based test entrance examination using evidence from post-UTME candidates in South East Nigeria. An ex-post facto design was used. The study involved a sample of 1,350 post-UTME candidates drawn from five states in South East of Nigeria using purposive sampling technique. A 20 item computer-based test questionnaire (CBTQ) developed by the researchers was used in data collection. Multiple regression was used in testing the hypothesis. Result showed that 2015 UTME candidates' ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches/timing of examination and sufficiency of examination centres significantly influenced their performance in CBT examination. It was recommended that candidates, JAMB and government should put their hands on desk to improve on the present condition, in order to achieve an optimal goal of CBT as a mode of entrance examination into Nigeria universities.

Keywords: CBT examination, ICT Skills, ICT facilities, batches of examination, examination centres, 2015 UTME candidates' performance.

Introduction

Since the inception of Joint Matriculation Board (JAMB) in 1978, the Board's mode of entrance examination into Nigeria Universities has been Paper Pencil Test (PPT). In order to actualize enhanced effective education in a highly competitive world today, which is the primary aim of Information Communication and Technology (ICT), JAMB introduced CBT as a mode of entrance examination into Nigeria universities in 2013.

In that 2013, UTME candidates were allowed to choose the mode of entrance examination of their choice. Few candidates chose CBT, preferring the conventional PPT or Dual Based Test (DBT) in which the questions were on the computer but the answers were shaded on a physical sheet. In 2014, JAMB reduced the number of PPT

centres, leading to increase in the enrolment for the DBT and CBT options. In 2015 JAMB introduced CBT as the only mode of entrance examination. This policy made by JAMB left UMTE candidates with no other option than to take CBT as their mode of entrance examination.

CBT means taking a test on computer instead of on paper (Dayo, 2012). One of the objectives of e-testing is to ensure 100 per cent elimination of all forms of examination malpractices that had been the major challenge in the conduct of public examination in the country. After the official announcement by the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) Executive Registrar, Professor Dibu Ojerinda and Minister of Education, Professor Ruqayyatu Rufa'i, that from 2013 CBT will be used to conduct UTME, reactions from the experts in education sector included benefits of CBT. Some of the benefits are; enhancing fair and precise evaluation of candidate's competency, rapid turnaround of exam results, more choices as to when and where to take the examination, easier registration and fortified examination security. Others saw it as development in the education sector as we are in the era of technology where students are expected to be information communication technology compliant.

Professor Adeyemi Isaac, the vice-chancellor, Bells University Ota, stated that there are some questions begging for answers if we are to operate computer-based test. "Do we have what it takes nationwide to operate it across board, or do we have to experiment it with selected few in some states?" Other reactions were, constant electricity supply must be put in place, unless there is an alternative means of getting it done, to bridge computer literacy gap between students in rural, urban, public and private schools and high and low income earners. Also, teaching the students how to use computer by adding it to their curriculum and equipping schools in Nigeria with computers before testing them through CBT. The claim of total freedom from examination malpractice was debunked by experts, stressing that corrupt data-base contractors could be bought over by unscrupulous students who are desperate to pass their examinations.

On the candidates' centres, reaction was that JAMB records over a million candidates annually which necessitate the body to randomly centre candidates among the 776 local government areas in Nigeria within the jurisdiction of their choice. It was argued that those might not be effective because already, those CBT centres available are not sufficient which periodically pose a problem to the body and consequently hinder effectiveness and efficiency in carrying out their activities or examinations. On the possibilities of providing computers for more than a million

candidates in a country that is regarded as underdeveloped, it was argued that this might be impossible to implement.

However, advantages of CBT have been enumerated by experts and researchers as follows.

- i. Lower long-term costs
- ii. Instant feedback to students
- iii. Improved reliability (machine marking is more reliable than human marking).
- iv. Greater storage efficiency -tens of thousands of answer scripts can be stored on a server compared to the physical space require for paper scripts.
- v. Enhanced question styles which incorporates interactive and multimedia.
- vi. Efficient administration.
- vii. Self-selection options for students.
- viii. Improved writing performance.
- ix. Efficient item development.
- x. Increased authenticity.
- xi. Potential to shift focus from assessment to instruction. (Becker, 2006: Salend, 2009).

Also, the demerits of CBT were highlighted as follows:

- i. It is expensive to establish
- ii. Not suitable for every type of assessment (such as extended response questions).
- iii. Additional training for candidates with disabilities.
- iv. Determine the best way to present some accommodations such as screen readers.

Challenges of effective implementation on of CBT in Nigeria as a developing country has also been identified to include the following:

- i. Level of ICT compliant of candidates
- ii. Times consuming factor
- iii. Monumental waste of resource.
- iv. Resources insufficiency
- v. Nigeria's electricity condition
- vi. Problem of non-simultaneous condition of examination.
- vii. Disclosure of examination questions by corrupt officials.
- viii. Mix-ups in result computation
- ix. Poor ICT infrastructure facilities.
- x. Insufficient examination centres.

The Nation Newspaper of 15th March, 2015 while writing on the experience of JAMB CBT candidates of 2015 observed that two issues stick out as a sore thumb in the conduct of the examination – scheduled time conduct of the examination and equipment failure.

In order to take CBT examination, the candidates are faced with many challenges that can affect their performance. The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches/timing of examination and sufficiency of examination centres on candidates performance in UTME 2015 in South East Nigeria. Consequently, this hypothesis is tested in the study: there is no joint and relative effect of ICT facilities, ICT skills, batches and examination centres on candidates performance in UTME 2015 in South East Nigeria.

Method

An ex-post facto design was adopted for the study. The population comprised of all the 2015 post-UTME candidates in the five states in south East Nigeria. The questionnaire which was titled “computer based test questionnaire” (CBTQ) comprises of two sections. Section A is the candidate’s 2015 UTME score, while section B comprises of 16 items which was responded to on four point liker scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). A random sample of 1,350 post-UTME candidates of 2015 responded to the questionnaire, which has a reliability index of 0.81. Out of 1,219 questionnaires that were returned, 1,108 was found fit and used for the study. Multiple regression was used to analyze the data.

Results

H₀₁: There is no joint and relative effect of ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches and exam centres on candidates’ performance in UTME 2015 in South East Nigeria.

Table 1: Joint and relative effect of ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches and examination centres on candidates’ performance in UTME 2015.

R	R ²	F	Sig	Variables	Beta	T	Sig
.122	.013	3.49	.008	ICT skills	0.09	-2.67	.01
				ICT facilities	0.02	.98	.33
				Batches	0.05	-1.50	.13
				Centres	0.05	-1.56	.12

Result in the above table shows that all the predictors, i.e. ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches in examination time and examination centres jointly are significant in predicting candidates' performance in 2015 UTME. It also revealed that 1.3% of the variance in candidates performance in 2015 UTME is jointly accounted for by ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches in examination time and examination centres.

The relative effect of the predictors as shown by their beta coefficients revealed that candidates ICT skills has significant effect on their performance in CBT of 2015 UTME. While ICT facilities, batches in CBT examination time table and CBT examination centres had no significant effect on candidates' performance in CBT in 2015 UTME.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations.

The result in the table above revealed that, candidates' ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches in examination time table and sufficiency of CBT examination centres have significant effect on candidates' performance in 2015 UTME.

The finding that ICT skill has a significant influence on candidates performance in CBT examination support those of Godley & Pedulla (2002) which reported that students' computer familiarity was significantly associated with test performance in CBTs: and finally concluded that students with lower computer familiarity scored lower on CBTs than students with moderate and higher computer familiarity. The implication of this observation is that there is a linear association between ICT skills and candidates performance in CBT examination.

Thus, emphasis should be on teaching the students on how to use computer by adding it to their curriculum. Also, equipping schools in Nigeria with computers to improve on the CBT computer skills of UTME candidates for optimal/performance should be implemented by the appropriate authority.

The result also lends support to agree on the reaction from the experts in education sector that to provide ICT facilities (computer, electricity, network service) for UTME will be impossible to implement by JAMB. The result is an indication that ICT facilities provided by JAMB for 2015 UTME were not adequate and also, to improve on the performance, more ICT facilities should be provided.

The finding that batches/time to write UTME has no significant influence on candidates performance disagrees with the stakeholders in education sector reaction that candidates could not meet up with the time of the examination. Thus, to improve on the candidates' performance, the three sessions should be reduced.

The result also revealed no significant influence of insufficient number of examination centres in 2015 UTME on candidates' performance. This finding disagrees with the masses resection that the UTME centres are not sufficient and

periodically pose a problem to JAMB and consequently, hinders effectiveness and efficiency in carrying out their activities or examination. Thus, to improve candidates' performance in the previous years, the JAMB Registrars' promise that "more examination centres would be secured before the conduct of next year examination" should be implemented.

The major findings of this study revealed that in 2015 CBT examination, candidates' ICT skills, ICT facilities, batches/timing of examination and sufficiency of examination centres affected their performance in UTME. Due to inclusion of ICTs in education, it is necessary to re-consider and rethink, modify or change the traditional examination methods. Computer based test as a mode of UTME has come to stay. It is therefore necessary for candidate, JAMB and government to put their hands on desk to improve on the available condition in order to achieve an optimal goal of CBT.

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